

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF UHF ANTENNA FOR BONE FRACTURE MONITORING

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Abstract

A bone fracture is a complete or partial break in the bone's connective tissue. Every bone within the body is prone to breaking. This paper demonstrates the development of an UHF antenna that may be employed for bone fracture monitoring. The proposed dipole antenna length is 135.13 mm, feeding gap is 20 mm and wire diameter is 5 mm. Proposed antenna operates from 824 MHz to 936 MHz with an impedance bandwidth of 112 MHz. A cylindrical bone fracture model is also designed with appropriate dielectric materials in CST. The difference of reflection co-efficient (S_{11}) between normal bone and fractured bone is the key factor for bone fracture monitoring. A single dipole antenna is used to observe the difference in reflection co-efficient (S_{11}) for bone fracture monitoring at three different positions inside the bone. Furthermore, dual dipole antenna has been designed to observe the difference of s-parameters between normal bone and fractured bone at three same different positions examined earlier.

Keywords: UHF, Dipole Antenna, S-Parameter, Bone Fracture, Phantom.

1. INTRODUCTION

A fracture is the term used in medicine to describe a fractured bone. Traumas like falls, auto accidents, or physical injury frequently result in fractures. Yet, some diseases and monotonous activities (like running) may raise ones chance of developing a certain form of fracture. To capture images of a fracture, at least one imaging test is required:

An X-ray can identify any fracture and demonstrate degree of bone damage. An MRI may be used by doctors to obtain a full view of damage to bones and surrounding tissues. The ligaments and cartilage that surround ones bones will also be seen on an MRI. Compared to an X-ray, a CT scan will provide doctors more detailed picture of the bone and the tissues around them. A brain scan is used by medical practitioners to find fractures that aren't evident on an X-ray.

The wireless transmission of data from sensors positioned on the fracture site makes antennas a crucial part of bone fracture tracking analysis. In order to watch the fracture in real-time without invasive treatments or bodily links, wireless transmission is essential. The movement and pressure of the bones are measured during bone fracture tracking by sensors positioned on the skin's surface close to the fracture location. For further study, these sensors produce electrical impulses that must be relayed to a receiver. These

impulses can now be transmitted wirelessly without the need for tangible connections thanks to antennas.

Several advantages of using antennas in bone fracture tracking research include:

- **Real-time monitoring:** Real-time tracking of the fracture site is made possible by the wireless signal transfer, allowing for the quick identification of any changes or anomalies.
- **Non-invasive:** Antennas take the place of invasive treatments or bodily links, lessening the possibility of infection and the patient's pain.
- **Improved accuracy:** Antennas offer a dependable and precise method of data transmission, lowering the possibility of errors and enhancing the analysis's general precision.
- **Greater convenience:** Wireless communication makes it possible for patients to walk around without limitation and go about their everyday lives in ease.

The use of antennas in bone fracture monitoring analysis is crucial for precise, ongoing observation of the fracture site and also increases patient satisfaction and efficiency. The fact that dipole antennas have several benefits over other kinds of antennas in this application makes them a popular choice for bone fracture monitoring analysis. Dipole antennas are an affordable option for wireless transmission in bone fracture monitoring devices because they are straightforward, effective, and simple to construct. The omnidirectional radiation pattern of dipole antennas, which radiates electromagnetic waves evenly in all directions perpendicular to the antenna's center, is one of their main benefits. Because it enables a wide coverage area around the fracture site and ensures that wireless signals are caught regardless of the direction of the sensors, this feature is especially helpful in bone fracture tracking systems. Dipole antennas also have the benefit of operating over a broad frequency range, enabling the propagation of various signal kinds. Dipole antennas can be used in bone fracture tracking devices to send both high-frequency signals, like strain data, and low-frequency signals, like temperature readings.

In conclusion, due to their omnidirectional radiation pattern, broad frequency range, and other advantages, dipole antennas are used in bone fracture tracking analysis. These characteristics make them a practical and affordable choice for wireless transmission in devices that track bone fractures.

- Using 73-ohm UHF antennas, this work introduces a new method of bone fracture tracking.
- The identification process is aided by single dipole antenna and placement of two similar antennas on the top and bottom sides to observe the difference in s-parameters depending on the position of the fracture.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The most frequent injuries associated with musculoskeletal damage are classified as bone fractures. In all hospitals across the world, a variety of procedures are used to analyze bone fractures. The most popular technique for analysis is x-ray, where the fracture's position and degree are determined by carefully scrutinizing the picture. Owing to imaging quality issues and overlaps between different anatomical components, radiologists frequently have trouble analyzing image. To address this issue, improved computer vision and a number of machine learning approaches have been proposed [1]. However, it is not practical to detect bone fractures using x-rays.

Implantable medical devices are now receiving more attention in the study of health care monitoring. The bulk of medical applications documented in the literature operate on medical devices and wireless transmission service that operates at 401-406 MHz [2-4] or at 2.44-2.46 MHz [5-7] in the ISM band, and operates largely in radio frequency band. Implanted antennas are often placed inside the muscles, fat, or just below the skin.

It is extremely difficult to develop implanting devices because of the body's massively complicated structure and the lossy qualities of tissues; in particular, biocompatibility might be a problem [8].

Non-invasive sensors offer convenience, durability, high level of protection against illness, cross-contamination, making them perfect for verification tasks (such as assessing patients' behavior, daily activities, and physiological capacity) [9, 10]. Despite all the medical advances, it could be difficult to employ wearable technology, especially on body radiators.

Due to interference effects, human body power absorption, and dielectric coupling, there is a potential that performance will suffer [11, 12].

Table I: Summary of Related Works

References	Antenna Type	Purpose
[3]	Microstrip Antenna	Communication with medical implants
[4]	Dual-band implantable antenna	Continuous glucose monitoring
[5]	Implanted cavity slot antenna	Embedding in human arm
[7]	Dipole antenna	Implantable retinal prosthesis
[15]	Dual Dipole Antenna	Bone Fracture Monitoring

3. SINGLE DIPOLE ANTENNA DESIGN

Diameter of dipole antenna is chosen to be 5 mm and gap of the feed point is chosen to be 20 mm. The impedance of port is chosen to be 73 ohm and length of the dipole is chosen to be 135.13 mm.

Figure 1: Single Dipole Antenna

3.1 S-Parameter Observation:

The behavior of radio frequency (RF) components and circuits, including antennas, is described by S-parameters, sometimes referred to as scattering parameters. The power that an antenna transmits and reflects at various frequencies is represented by the S-parameters of the antenna. The power that is redirected toward its source as a result of impedance mismatch between the antennas and the transmission system or the surroundings is described by the S_{11} characteristic of a dipole antenna. It is sometimes referred to as the reflection coefficient, and it often takes the shape of a complicated diagram.

Figure 2: S-parameter observation at 874.4 MHz

A low s-parameter of -14.96 dB is obtained at 874.4 MHz shown in fig 2. The impedance bandwidth is 112 MHz.

3.2 VSWR Observation:

Figure 3: VSWR observation at 874.4 MHz

An antenna's impedance matching to a transmission line or feedline is gauged using the voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR). A completely matched antenna will have a VSWR of 1:1, which means that the antenna is radiating all of the power delivered down the transmission line. The diameter of the elements, the feedpoint position, the frequency of operation, and the length of the antenna can all have an impact on a dipole antenna's VSWR. Over a wide frequency range, the usual VSWR of a dipole antenna is modest, often 1.5:1 or less. Figure 3 shows that VSWR for single dipole antenna is 1.44.

3.3 Far-Field Polar Plot Observation:

Figure 4: Far-field polar plot output at 874.4 MHz

The azimuthal angle, which is the angle around a circle centered on the antenna, is shown by the horizontal axis in this polar figure. The elevation angle, which is the angle above or below the horizontal plane passing through the antenna, is represented by the vertical axis.

The figure displays the antenna's radiation pattern in the far field, i.e., how the antenna radiates energy when it is located a fair distance from the antenna. The antenna radiates identically in all directions in the horizontal plane because the plot is symmetric on the horizontal axis. Two lobes are depicted in the vertical plane, one pointing upward and the other below, indicating that the antenna emits more radiation in those directions than in other directions. Figure 4 shows that the radiation pattern of the proposed dipole antenna is omnidirectional.

3.4 Far-Field Gain Observation:

Figure 5: Far-field gain output at 874.4 MHz

An antenna's capability to emit electrical radiation in a given direction is gauged by its far field gain. It is described as the difference between the amount of energy an antenna radiates in one direction and the amount of energy it would radiate if it radiated evenly in all directions. An antenna's directivity, or capacity to concentrate radiation in a certain direction, is measured. When compared to an isotropic radiator, which radiates equally in all directions, a dipole antenna's far-field gain is a measurement of the power emitted by the antenna in a specific direction. A typical way to measure an antenna's far-field gain is in decibels relative to isotropy, or dBi. Figure 5 shows far-field gain of dipole antenna is 2.026 dBi at 874.4 MHz.

3.5 E Field Distribution:

Figure 6: E field distribution at 874.4 MHz

The element of the electrical waves known as the E field is what gives the antenna its electrical charges and current flow. It is an unit vector that specifies the direction and strength of electric field around the antenna at every point in space. The current and voltage distributions along the antenna has a direct impact on the E field, which in turn influences the antenna's emission pattern and efficiency. Figure 6 shows the maximum electric field (E field) of single dipole antenna at 874.4 MHz is 13883.2 V/m.

3.6 H Field Distribution:

Figure 7: H field distribution at 874.4 MHz

The part of the electromagnetic force called the H field is what causes the magnetic energy and flow of current in the antenna. It is an unit vector that specifies the magnetic field's intensity and direction at each location in the area surrounding the antenna. The current network along the antenna has a direct impact on the H field, which in turn influences the antenna's emission pattern and effectiveness. Figure 7 shows the maximum magnetic field (H field) of single dipole antenna at 874.4 MHz is 101.236 A/m.

Table II: Simulated Results Analysis for Single Dipole Antenna at 874.4 MHz

S- Parameter	VSWR	E Field	H Field	Far-Field
S ₁₁	VSWR	V/m	A/m	Gain
-14.96 dB	1.44	13883.2	101.236	2.026 dBi

4. BONE FRACTURE PHANTOM DESIGN

Table III: Properties for Bone Fracture Phantom [14]

Properties	Model of Bone Fracture Phantom	
	Bone	Fracture (Blood)
Dielectric Constant [ϵ_r]	6.25	80
Mue [μ]	1	1
Electrical Conductivity [S/m]	0.28	2.19

In the CST Microwave studio, a phantom is created to replicate the bone fracture seen in fig 8. With the use of a cylindrical model, the arm anatomy is replicated. The bone's dimensions are 110 mm by 150 mm, and Table III lists its UHF properties in a

straightforward form. Cylindrical model with dimensions of 15 mm by 70 mm is used to replicate the fracture with the UHF characteristics specified in Table III [14].

Figure 8: Cylindrical model of bone fracture

5. SIMULATION RESULTS ANALYSIS

5.1 Single Dipole Antenna:

Figure 9 shows a simulation model of a bone without fracture with a radius of 55 mm and a length of 150 mm. For fracture monitoring, a cylindrical inclusion resembling blood is injected. The inclusion is positioned at 3 different locations at 697.3 MHz to study the effects of various locations on s-parameters and track changes.

Figure 9: Single dipole antenna without fracture

Due to this, three places are chosen, shown in fig 10. The second place is the bone's core, as indicated in fig 11. The final location is the bottom side shown in fig 12.

Figure 10: Bone fracture inclusion on top side for single dipole antenna

Figure 11: Bone fracture inclusion in the center for single dipole antenna

Figure 12: Bone fracture inclusion on bottom side for single dipole antenna

Figure 13: Power reflection coefficient- S_{11} for single dipole antenna

The value of S_{11} without fracture is -39.16 dB at 697.3 MHz. Observation of bone fracture at 3 different positions has also been observed at 697.3 MHz. There is a significant change in the value of S_{11} compared to no inclusion when bone fracture inclusion on top side which is -15.78 dB. In case of bone fracture inclusion in the center the value of S_{11} slightly changed compared to no inclusion which is -33.97 dB. On the contrary, when the bone fracture inclusion is on bottom side the value of S_{11} is quite similar to the case of no inclusion which is -39.51 dB. So, to get improved results we observed the s-parameters variations for dual dipole antenna for no inclusion of bone and inclusion of fractured bone at 3 different positions at 697.3 MHz.

5.2 Dual Dipole Antenna:

Figure 14 shows a simulation model of bone without fracture with a radius of 55 mm and a length of 150 mm. Fractures can be found by placing UHF recommended antennas on top and bottom sides of the arm design. For fracture monitoring, a cylindrical inclusion resembling blood is injected. The inclusion is positioned at 3 different locations, much as it would be with a single dipole antenna operating at 697.3 MHz, to study the effects of various locations on s-parameters and monitor changes.

Figure 14: Dual dipole antenna without fracture

Due to this, three places are chosen, shown in fig 15. The second place is the bone's core, as indicated in fig 16. The final location is the bottom side shown in fig 17.

Figure 15: Bone fracture inclusion on top side for dual dipole antenna

Figure 16: Bone fracture inclusion in the center for dual dipole antenna

Figure 17: Bone fracture inclusion on bottom side for dual dipole antenna.

Figure 18: Power reflection coefficient-S₁₁ & S₂₂ for dual dipole antenna

- I. If there is no inclusion, the antennas' S₁₁ and S₂₂ are comparable. The numbers specifically demonstrate that antennas 1 and 2 have power reflection coefficients of -51.02 dB and -52.22 dB at 697.3 MHz, respectively. The mesh grid asymmetries may be the cause of the little discrepancy between the S₁₁ and S₂₂. Additionally, S₁₁ and S₂₂ can be shown to vary from having no inclusion to having an inclusion in the center, suggesting the existence of a bone lesion and emphasizing the distinction between non-fractured and fractured bone.
- II. Whenever the inclusion is in the top side, S₁₁ and S₂₂ are, respectively, -15.86 dB and -38.16 dB at 697.3 MHz. The inclusion is now close to antenna 1, which increases the power reflection to antenna 1 and helps to explain this disparity.

- III. Whenever the inclusion is in the center position, S_{11} and S_{22} are, respectively, -38.71 dB and -36.31 dB at 697.3 MHz meaning that both the antennas are in equal distance from the center.
- IV. Whenever the inclusion is in the bottom side, S_{11} and S_{22} are, respectively, -45.69 dB and -15.56 dB at 697.3 MHz. It is possible to understand this large discrepancy by noticing that inclusion is close to antenna 2, which amplifies the radiation reflected to antenna 2.

6. CONCLUSION

The comparable result analysis demonstrates that by considering s-parameter, two comparable UHF antennas might well be employed to track a bone lesion. These results can be used to detect non-invasive bone fractures. The subsequent phases involve examining polarization and creating a more accurate model using materials including skin, fat, muscles, bone and blood. The consequences of wireless transmission devices' interference on UHF networks must be considered and addressed.

Data Availability Statement

No data used in this research.

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Conflict of Interest & Fund

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Authors Contribution

FR and SMRI conceived the presented idea, developed the theory, performed the computations, and verified the analytical methods. Both presented, the idea, data collection, the method developed and the manuscript edited. All authors discussed the results and contributed to the final manuscript.

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